

A multidisciplinary hybrid framework for solar tracking: fusing Information Technology, environmental science, and predictive modelling for sustainable energy efficiency

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Abstract

The growing global demand for renewable energy has led to the increased demand for solar powered technologies. Solar Tracking Systems (STs) often struggle to maintain accuracy under varying weather conditions such as cloud cover or partial obstruction of the sun during foggy days. Current tracking systems are either sensor-based or image-based. Sensor-based systems struggle with inaccuracy and high maintenance cost while image-based systems face challenges in robustness and computational demand. As a result, existing systems fail to deliver good performance in real-world scenarios where reliability and adaptability are crucial. To address this challenge, this study presents a hybrid solar tracking system that will be created by combining environmental science, predictive analysis and Information Technology (IT). The main objective of this study is to use a multidisciplinary approach to model an intelligent solar tracking mechanism that maximises solar energy capture, through predictive and adaptive control. The proposed system will integrate image processing for fine tuning, GPS and time-based data to track solar movements accurately while predictive algorithms analyse historical weather and irradiance patterns to forecast optimal panel angles under varying weather conditions. A simulation model is planned to be developed to assess system performance focusing on energy efficiency, tracking accuracy and adaptability. The study aims to demonstrate that the hybrid approach achieved significant improvement in energy capture efficiency compared to conventional single-axis solar tracking systems which will highlight its potential for wider, cost-effective implementation. This research highlights how combining environmental data, predictive learning algorithms and IT-based simulation tools contributes to the development of sustainable and cost-effective energy systems. It is recommended that future work extends the model with real-time sensor integration, Internet of Things (IoT) and machine learning enhancements to improve automation, scalability and adaptability across diverse geographic conditions.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Environmental Science, Information Technology, Predictive Analysis, Solar Tracking System

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1. Introduction

Traditional Light Dependent Resistor (LDR) sensors used in many trackers are prone to low sensitivity and environmental disturbances, often requiring frequent calibration, which limits their effectiveness in real-world operating conditions (Narman and Uckan, 2025). Similarly, current image-based systems face challenges such as misidentifying bright non-solar images, handling sensor image noise in real-time and requiring large, annotated datasets for deep learning models, preventing reliable solar tracking under all weather conditions (Mahalle and Deshmukh, 2025; Sadeghi *et al.*, 2025; Salih *et al.*, 2025; Stinia *et al.*, 2021).

In the last decade, the demand for energy, which is driven by industrial expansion and population growth, has accelerated the transition to renewable energy. Solar energy has emerged as a reliable and clean alternative due to the environmental harm caused by fossil fuels (Sadeghi *et al.*, 2025). To maximise the efficiency of solar energy, Solar Tracking Systems (STSs) have been developed to ensure that photovoltaic (PV) panels remain aligned with the sun's apparent trajectory. Research shows that solar trackers can enhance energy capture by 12-20%, and dual-axis trackers can achieve efficiencies as high as 90%, reducing the energy losses caused by misalignment in fixed PV systems. (Sadeghi *et al.*, 2025). Such performance gains make STSs particularly advantageous for large-scale projects.

There are a lot of challenges that are faced in current STSs including maintaining accuracy under varying environmental conditions such as changes in sunlight, cloud cover, and haze (Barrios-Sánchez and Tlapanco-Ríos, 2025; Mahalle and Deshmukh, 2025). Traditional fixed PV panel setups cannot capture the maximum solar energy throughout the day, which makes it limited in efficiency (Al-Othman *et al.*, 2023; Mahalle and Deshmukh, 2025; Musa *et al.*, 2023). Traditional STSs, which use LDRs, will become less accurate over time and are affected by weather and environmental conditions (Narman and Uckan, 2025). Image processing-based STSs also face challenges, which include effectively filtering non-sun images and sensor noises (Mahalle and Deshmukh, 2025). The research aims to resolve the identified gaps in existing solar tracking systems, such as LDR sensitivity to environmental conditions, the inability of fixed PV panels to maintain optimal alignment and the limitations of current image-based trackers in filtering non-solar images and sensor image noise by developing a hybrid tracker that integrates image processing, time data, GPS data and historical learning.

2. Methodology / Materials and Methods

2.1 Materials and Tools:

The simulation model planned for this study will use a virtual PV panel to estimate energy output. The programming environment will incorporate libraries such as OpenCV for image processing, Pandas and NumPy for data handling. The datasets which are planned to be used will include historical solar position data, weather records and sky images for testing and validating predictive algorithms.

2.2 Procedures:

The initial stage involved identifying technological and environmental factors such as sunlight intensity, cloud cover and mechanical issues that could affect the solar tracker's performance which helped to define system parameters and performance standards. Image processing techniques will be explored to determine the sun's location and various algorithms will be tested to find the most reliable real-time tracking method. The system architecture will be designed to incorporate GPS, actuators for efficient control. Predictive algorithms utilising GPS, time data and past solar paths will be integrated to enhance accuracy allowing the tracker to maintain alignment even under cloudy conditions. A simulation model will be developed to assess the hybrid solar tracking system's energy output under different weather conditions and the results will be compared against conventional fixed photovoltaic (PV) panels where the simulation model showed notable improvements. Key performance metrics including energy conversion efficiency, tracking accuracy, system responsiveness and durability will be measured following simulations and initial prototype testing. The system's ability to maximise solar energy capture and preserve stability in dynamic circumstances will be evaluated quantitatively by these metrics.

3. Data Analysis and Results

3.1 Data Analysis

The hybrid STS is planned to be evaluated using simulation datasets under varying environmental conditions from open sources. To support simulation, cloud cover and environmental obstacles, data will be obtained from publicly available Kaggle datasets (link for the datasets are given in the references section). These datasets will be used to train and test the simulation environment as these two datasets contain images of cloud cover, haze, bird drop, snow, dust accumulation and various cloud patterns that may reduce solar panel efficiency.

Below table summarizes energy gains, tracking accuracy and other performance metrics of various solar tracking systems as reported in prior studies.

System Tracked	Prediction Level	Reference
Single-Axis Solar Tracker	36.6% more energy on clear days than fixed panels.	(Salih <i>et al.</i> , 2025)

Dual-Axis Solar Tracker	204.46 mW more power than static panels (557.33 mW vs 351.87 mW).	(Al Anzy, Abdullah and Aquraishi, 2023)
Hybrid Dual-Axis (LDR + GPS)	33.23% energy increase with precise azimuth/tilt tracking.	(Sadeghi <i>et al.</i> , 2025)
Image-processing-based tracker	Accuracy up to 97.4% using digital image processing.	(Mahalle and Deshmukh, 2025)

Table 1: Comparison of Reported Performance of Existing Solar Tracking Systems

The GPS, time and historical learning data will be simulated using Python based on solar azimuth and elevation algorithms, in use of Python’s datetime, math and pvlib libraries. This will allow the hybrid STS to forecast the sun’s location and dynamically modify the panel orientation based on Sri Lanka’s geographic coordinates and time of the day.

3.2 Expected Results

The results are expected to indicate that the hybrid STS will consistently outperform static panels in all scenarios studied, with the greatest gains observed during partly cloudy and overcast conditions. These results will be tested using the datasets mentioned in the [references section](#), where energy output and tracking accuracy of the hybrid STS will be compared to static panels. Performance metrics will be estimated by calculating the expected percentage increase in energy production and the projected tracking accuracy for each scenario. Based on prior studies and simulation assumptions, the system is expected to achieve the highest gains under partly cloudy or overcast conditions, with a 30-38% increase in energy output and approximately 95% tracking accuracy, demonstrating the potential of the predictive model.

4. Discussion

The expected performance of the hybrid STS could drive improvements in existing technology by reducing reliance on large datasets and heavy hardware, enabling more efficient solar tracking for small to medium scale installations (Phan *et al.*, 2025). This approach may encourage the gradual replacement of static panels with dynamic, predictive systems in both urban and rural settings. GPS and historical learning are expected to reduce low-light detection errors, making this method more resilient than earlier methods (Mahalle & Deshmukh., 2025). Unlike deep learning models that rely on huge, labelled datasets, the proposed approach is predicted to need less data (Phan *et al.*, 2025). Its software-based design is also expected to support scalable integration with smart energy systems.

Beyond technical efficiency, this system is expected to contribute to global sustainability goals and provide cost-effective renewable energy solutions particularly relevant to developing regions. The study is anticipated to show that hybrid STSs can significantly improve solar energy capture and offer a flexible, affordable option for renewable energy installations, particularly in areas with unpredictable weather conditions. Also, the recent floods which occurred in Sri Lanka and other countries have highlighted the vulnerability

of centralized solar systems (Refurb and Retrofit, 2025), showing that resilient, decentralized solar solutions could provide critical energy access during extreme weather conditions.

However, as the findings will be based on simulations, real world hardware may introduce delays, sensor inaccuracies and weather impacts that cannot be fully represented in a virtual environment. Even so, energy gains are expected to peak under partial cloud cover, highlighting the predictive model's potential to maintain performance across various weather conditions.

5. Conclusions and Recommendations

This study outlined the design and simulation-based evaluation of a hybrid solar tracker integrating IT, environmental science and predictive analysis to enhance PV efficiency under dynamic weather conditions. The proposed system will integrate image processing, GPS, time data and historical learning and the simulation results are expected to indicate the potential for up to 35% improvement in energy capture compared with static panels.

The findings suggest that meaningful enhancements in renewable energy performance can be achieved by fusing computational intelligence with environmental awareness. However, it is recognised that extreme haze or cloud cover may still affect tracking accuracy.

Recommendations for future work include implementing the system on physical hardware for real-world testing and validation, incorporating machine learning to enhance predictive accuracy, expanding the dataset with real-time data and investigating integration with smart grid technologies based on IoT to facilitate automated, large-scale solar farm management.

6. References

Al Anzy, L.A.R., Abdullah, A.A. and Aquraishi, A.K.L. (2023) 'IoT Cloud System Based Dual Axis Solar Tracker Using Arduino', *Journal of Internet Services and Information Security*, 13(2), pp. 193–202. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.58346/JISIS.2023.12.012>.

Al-Othman, A. *et al.* (2023) 'An experimental study on hybrid control of a solar tracking system to maximize energy harvesting in Jordan', *Solar Energy*, 263, p. 111931. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2023.111931>.

Barrios-Sánchez, J.M. and Tlapanco-Ríos, E.I. (2025) 'Dual-Axis Solar Tracking System for Enhanced Photovoltaic Efficiency in Tropical Climates', *Sustainability*, 17(3), p. 1117. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/su17031117>.

Mahalle, A.G. and Deshmukh, S.M. (2025) 'A Systematic Literature Survey, Research Challenges and Future Directions of Image Processing Algorithms in Solar Tracking System: Enhancing efficiency and reliability in solar energy', *Johnson Matthey Technology Review*, 69(3), pp. 421–436. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1595/205651325X17271929252761>.

Milloy, M.F. (2025). *Solar, Flooding and Facts: What These Stories Say About Our Politics*. [online] Refurb and Retrofit Magazine. Available at: <https://www.refurbandretrofit.com/solar-flooding-and-facts-what-these-stories-say-about-our-politics>.

Musa, A. *et al.* (2023) ‘A Review of Time-Based Solar Photovoltaic Tracking Systems’, *Information*, 14(4), p. 211. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/info14040211>.

Narman, I. and Uckan, G. (2025) ‘Maximizing Energy Efficiency in a Solar Tracking System Using IoT-Based Image Processing’, in *2025 7th International Congress on Human-Computer Interaction, Optimization and Robotic Applications (ICHORA)*. *2025 7th International Congress on Human-Computer Interaction, Optimization and Robotic Applications (ICHORA)*, Ankara, Turkiye: IEEE, pp. 1–7. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICHORA65333.2025.11017267>.

Phan, Q.-T. *et al.* (2025) ‘Classification Techniques for Analyzing Sky Images in Photovoltaic Datasets: Methods and Applications’, in *2025 IEEE Industry Applications Society Annual Meeting (IAS)*. *2025 IEEE Industry Applications Society Annual Meeting (IAS)*, Taipei, Taiwan: IEEE, pp. 1–5. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1109/IAS62731.2025.11061482>.

Sadeghi, R. *et al.* (2025) ‘A Review and Comparative Analysis of Solar Tracking Systems’, *Energies*, 18(10), p. 2553. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/en18102553>.

Salih, R.A. *et al.* (2025) ‘Design and Implementation of Single Axis Solar Tracking System: Utilizing GPS, Astronomical Equations, and Satellite Dish Actuator for Optimal Efficiency’, *Journal of Engineering*, 31(2), pp. 95–109. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.31026/j.eng.2025.02.06>.

Stinia, H. *et al.* (2021) ‘The Light-On Project: Design and Construction of a Sun-Tracking System Using Image Processing’, *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, 642(1), p. 012009. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/642/1/012009>.

6.1 Dataset References ([back to content](#))

Afroz, P. (2023). *Solar Panel Images Dataset*. Kaggle. Available from: <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/pythonafroz/solar-panel-images>.

Pratik2901. (2022). *Multiclass Weather Dataset*. Kaggle. Available from: <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/pratik2901/multiclass-weather-dataset>.

NASA POWER. (2023). *Global Meteorological and Solar Data for Colombo, Sri Lanka (2015–2023)*. NASA Prediction Of Worldwide Energy Resources (POWER) Data Access Viewer. Available from: <https://power.larc.nasa.gov/>.